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Effect of Inulin Supplementation on Testicular Tissue in Mice

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ABSTRACT

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The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of inulin supplementation on spermatogenesis in testicular tissue of mice. The main function of the testis is the production of androgens and spermatozoa. Oral inulin administration was observed to increase the number of Leydig cells and spermatozoa. Six-week-old male BALB/c mice were used in the experiment, divided into two groups: a control group and an inulin group (n=15). The control group was fed standard feed and water, while the inulin group received water containing 10% inulin for 7 weeks. At the end of the experiment, the animals were sacrificed under ketamine/xylazine anesthesia, and testicular tissues were fixed in 10% formalin. After routine histological processing, 4–5 µm thick sections were taken from paraffin blocks and stained with hematoxylin-eosin and Masson's trichrome. The preparations were examined under a light microscope. In the inulin-treated group, fuller seminiferous tubules and an increased tendency towards germinative epithelial thickness were observed. The regular arrangement of spermatogonia, primary and secondary spermatocytes, and spermatids was maintained along the germinative epithelium, while an increased density of mature spermatozoa was observed in the lumen. Sertoli cells were observed to be located close to the basal membrane and to have normal morphology. Leydig cells in the interstitial space were also clearly observed. In the inulin group, the spermatogenesis process was observed to be more active compared to the control group, and the overall tissue integrity was preserved. In conclusion, it was observed that inulin application supported spermatogenesis in testicular tissue and created a tendency to increase the number of spermatogonia. Based on the evaluation of the obtained findings, it is thought that inulin may have positive effects on the male reproductive system and can be used as a supportive agent for infertility. However, further molecular and quantitative studies are needed to more clearly demonstrate these effects.

I. INTRODUCTION

In mammals, the testes originate from the intermediate mesoderm and are responsible for the production of spermatozoa and androgens (Major et al., 2021). Spermatogenesis takes place within the seminiferous tubules through a highly coordinated process involving mitotic, meiotic, and differentiation phases, ultimately leading to the formation of mature spermatozoa (Stanton, 2016; Ibtisham et al., 2017).

The proper functioning of spermatogenesis depends on the structural and functional integrity of testicular cells, particularly Sertoli and Leydig cells. Sertoli cells regulate germ cell development, maintain the microenvironment of the seminiferous epithelium, and form the blood–testis barrier (BTB), which protects developing germ cells from immunological attack (Mäkelä et al., 2019; Stanton, 2016). Leydig cells, located in the interstitial tissue, are responsible for testosterone production, which is essential for the maintenance of spermatogenesis (Mäkelä et al., 2019).

Spermatogenesis begins with spermatogonia located near the basal lamina, which undergo mitotic divisions and differentiate into primary and secondary spermatocytes. These cells subsequently undergo meiosis to form haploid spermatids, which further differentiate into mature spermatozoa through spermiogenesis (Ibtisham et al., 2017). The organization and continuity of these stages are critical for normal male fertility.

Male infertility is a significant global health problem, affecting approximately 15% of couples, with male-related factors accounting for nearly 30–40% of

cases (Erdemir et al., 2020). Various factors such as oxidative stress, environmental toxins, hormonal imbalance, and lifestyle conditions may negatively affect spermatogenesis and sperm quality. Therefore, identifying natural compounds that support testicular function has become an important area of research.

Cichorium intybus L., commonly known as chicory, is a plant widely used for its medicinal properties and rich bioactive content (Janda et al., 2021). It contains high levels of inulin, a natural polysaccharide with prebiotic properties that positively influences gut microbiota and exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (Lavrishcheva et al., 2022; Janda et al., 2021). Due to these properties, inulin has attracted attention for its potential protective effects on various tissues, including the reproductive system.

Previous studies have demonstrated that *Cichorium intybus* extracts may improve reproductive parameters by reducing oxidative stress and enhancing antioxidant enzyme activity in testicular tissue (Dorostghoal et al., 2020). Additionally, inulin supplementation has been associated with increased sperm count and improved hormonal profiles in experimental models (Fakher et al., 2023). These findings suggest that inulin may contribute to the preservation of spermatogenic cell organization and support overall testicular function.

Despite these promising findings, the histological effects of inulin supplementation on spermatogenesis remain insufficiently characterized. Therefore, the aim of this study was to histologically evaluate the effects of inulin supplementation on spermatogenesis in the testicular tissue of mice.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This project investigated the effect of the prebiotic substance inulin on the testicular tissue of mice. Two different groups were created using 6-week-old male BALB/c mice. The first group was the control group (CG) and was fed standard mouse food and normal water. The second group was designated as the inulin group (IG) and was given standard food along with water containing 10% inulin. The experiment was planned with 15 mice in each group.

The mice were fed ad libitum for 7 weeks at the Siirt University Experimental Animal Application and Research Center at 22 °C, in a 12-hour light and 12-hour dark cycle. The 6-week-old mice were randomly placed in cages of 3 each, and the control and inulin groups were kept in separate cages. A total of 5 control group cages and 5 inulin group cages were created. The standard mouse diet used during the experiment contained 58% carbohydrates (5.2% fiber), 29% protein, and 13% fat, and no changes were made to the diet composition. The mice were weighed at the end of the seven-week feeding period. At the end of the experiment, the animals were sacrificed under ketamine/xylazine anesthesia and cervical dislocation was performed. Testicular tissues were fixed in 10% formalin. After routine histological processing, the tissues were embedded in paraffin blocks, and 4–5 µm thick sections were taken from these blocks. Hematoxylin-eosin and Masson's trichrome staining were applied to the sections. The prepared slides were examined under a light microscope (Olympus BX51).

3. RESULTS

In the inulin-treated group, seminiferous tubules appeared more prominent and fuller compared to the control group (Figure 2). In addition, an increased tendency in spermatozoa density within the lumen was observed (Figure 2).

In the control group, seminiferous tubules contained germ cells at various developmental stages; however, spermatozoa density within the lumen was lower (Figure 1).

The regular arrangement of primary and secondary spermatocytes and spermatids along the germinal epithelium was preserved in both groups (Figures 1 and 2). However, cellular organization appeared more compact in the inulin group (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Histological view of testicular tissue from the control group. Seminiferous tubules contain germ cells at different stages of spermatogenesis, including spermatogonia located adjacent to the basal lamina, primary spermatocytes in the adluminal compartment, and spermatids approaching the luminal region. Mature spermatozoa are also observed within the lumen. The tubule lumen (red arrow), spermatozoa tails within the lumen (green arrow), spermatogonia near the basal lamina (yellow arrow), and developing germ cells within the seminiferous epithelium (blue arrow) are visible. Stained with hematoxylin-eosin (H&E). Magnification: ×20

Fig 2. Histological view of testicular tissue from the inulin-treated group. Seminiferous tubules exhibit germ cells at different developmental stages, including spermatogonia adjacent to the basal lamina, primary and secondary spermatocytes within the seminiferous epithelium, spermatids near the luminal region, and mature spermatozoa within the lumen. The tubule lumen (red arrow), spermatogonia near the basal lamina (yellow arrow), developing germ cells within the seminiferous epithelium (blue arrow), and spermatozoa tails in the lumen (green arrow) are visible. Stained with hematoxylin-eosin (H&E). Magnification: $\times 20$.

Fig. 3. Histological view of the testicular capsule (tunica albuginea). Dense connective tissue structures and collagen fibers are clearly visualized using Masson's trichrome staining. The tunica albuginea forming the testicular capsule is indicated by the arrow. Magnification: $\times 20$.

Sertoli cells were observed near the basal membrane with normal morphology in both groups (Figures 1 and 2), while Leydig cells in the interstitial area were clearly distinguishable (Figures 1 and 2).

In sections stained with Masson's trichrome, connective tissue and collagen fibers were clearly visualized (Figures 3 and 4). The tunica albuginea forming the testicular capsule was distinctly observed (Figure 3).

No structural deterioration was observed in the inulin group, and overall tissue integrity was preserved (Figure 5).

4. DISCUSSION

In one study, lipid peroxidation levels were reduced using *Cichorium intybus* leaf extract. As a result, SOD and GPx activity increased in the testes, leading to an improvement in testicular oxidative status. *Cichorium intybus* leaf extract increased antioxidant enzyme activities (Dorostghoal et al., 2020). The findings from this study are consistent with the preservation of seminiferous tubule structure and the regular organization of the germinative epithelium observed in our study, suggesting a possible protective role of inulin on testicular tissue through its antioxidant effects. In another study, diazinon toxin was administered intraperitoneally to adult male BALB/c mice, and the therapeutic potential of inulin extract was investigated. While diazinon negatively affected sperm quality and testicular tissue, inulin extract demonstrated antioxidant effects at different doses (Ahmadi et al., 2021). In line with these findings, the preservation of spermatogenic cell lineage and the

Fig. 4. Histological view of testicular tissue from the control group stained with Masson's trichrome. Seminiferous tubules and interstitial spaces are clearly visible. Germ cells at various stages of spermatogenesis are observed, including spermatogonia near the basal lamina, primary spermatocytes within the seminiferous epithelium, and spermatids toward the luminal compartment, along with spermatozoa within the lumen. The tubule lumen (red arrow), spermatozoa tails within the lumen (green arrow), spermatogonia near the basal lamina (yellow arrow), and developing germ cells within the seminiferous epithelium (blue arrow) are visible. Collagen fibers in the interstitial tissue are distinctly stained. Magnification: $\times 20$.

fuller appearance of seminiferous tubules in the inulin-treated group in our study support the spermatogenesis-enhancing potential of inulin.

Studies evaluating hormonal parameters have reported that inulin administration increased sperm count along with elevated FSH, LH, and testosterone levels (Fakher et al., 2023). Similarly, the increased spermatozoon density observed in the lumen of seminiferous tubules in our study supports the idea that inulin may positively influence male reproductive functions.

In studies conducted on healthy adult male Wistar rats, *Cichorium intybus* extract has been shown to improve oxidative status and reproductive parameters (Dorostghoal et al., 2019). Consistent

with these findings, the preservation of cellular organization and the clear identification of Leydig cells in our study further support the beneficial effects of inulin on testicular tissue.

Another study reported that *Cichorium intybus* extract increased spermatozoon count, spermatogenesis index, and seminiferous tubule diameter (Babenko et al., 2024). Although quantitative analysis was not performed in our study, the observed increase in spermatozoon density and preserved tissue architecture are in agreement with these findings. It has been reported that high doses of *Cichorium intybus* extracts do not produce toxic effects (Tatlı-Çankaya et al., 2014). Similarly, no structural deterioration was observed in the testicular tissue of the inulin-treated group in our study, supporting the safety of inulin administration.

Figure 5. Histological view of testicular tissue from the inulin-treated group stained with Masson's trichrome. Seminiferous tubules exhibit preserved architecture with germ cells at different developmental stages, including spermatogonia adjacent to the basal lamina, primary and secondary spermatocytes within the seminiferous epithelium, spermatids near the luminal region, and spermatozoa within the lumen. The tubule lumen (red arrow), spermatozoa tails within the lumen (green arrow), spermatogonia near the basal lamina (yellow arrow), and developing germ cells within the seminiferous epithelium (blue arrow) are discernible. Magnification: $\times 20$.

In toxicity models induced by CCl₄, chicory root extract has been shown to exert protective effects against testicular damage (Ghadi et al., 2019). In our study, the preservation of seminiferous tubule organization and tissue integrity suggests that inulin may exhibit similar protective properties.

In studies investigating sperm cryopreservation, inulin has been reported to improve sperm quality (Rahimi et al., 2024). The increased spermatozoon density observed in our findings supports these results and indicates a positive role of inulin in maintaining sperm function.

In line with all these findings, it is thought that inulin may support spermatogenesis by preserving cellular organization in testicular tissue. However, the main limitation of our study is that the evaluations were qualitative. Future studies including quantitative analysis, immunohistochemical markers, and oxidative stress parameters will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms underlying these effects.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, spermatogenesis was more active in testicular tissue and an increased tendency towards spermatogonia levels was observed in the group treated with inulin. The findings suggest that inulin may have positive effects on the male reproductive system. However, quantitative analyses and further studies at the molecular level are needed to better demonstrate this effect.

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Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Siirt University Local Ethics Committee for Animal Experiments (Decision date: 29/11/2024, Decision number: 2024/09/61).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this study.

Author Contributions

Experimental procedures were conducted by Günsel KİRMAN. Mehmet Sefa ULUTAŞ; contributed to the planning of the study and sample collection. The manuscript was written and finalized with the contributions of all authors.

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